

Importance of cation- π interactions in the conformational stability and specificity of β -lactamases

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Abstract : β -Lactamase production is the most common mechanism of resistance shown by bacteria against the β -lactam antibiotics. Extensive and irresponsible use of antibiotic agents leads to the emergence of these resistance strains. Hence in the present study we intend to explore the implication of cation- π interacting residues in preserving the conformation of β -lactamases. Analysis of intramolecular contacts between cation- π interacting residues shows that these residues contribute extensively to the overall stability of β -lactamases. It is also interesting to find that significant numbers of interacting residues are evolutionary conserved revealing the impact of these residues in determining the structural stability of β -lactamases. The outcome of our study provides crucial information about constancy pattern of β -lactamases and the strategies revealed in this study could be applied to design effective inhibitors.

Keywords : β -Lactamases, β -lactamase inhibitors, cation- π interactions, environmental preferences.

Introduction

Cation- π interactions contribute significantly to the conformational stability of proteins¹. Many researchers have stressed the importance of cation- π interactions in the stability and specificity of proteins²⁻⁵. Selective pressure created by the extensive use of antibiotics leads to the emergence and spread of β -lactam resistant strains. This impelled us to explore the importance of cation- π interacting residues in the functional specification of β -lactamases. Our results provide valuable insights to understand the mechanisms responsible for the stability of β -lactamases and offers promising strategy to design effective inhibitors.

Experimental

Retrieval of β -lactamase structures :

Three dimensional structures of β -lactamases were retrieved from Protein Data Bank (PDB)⁶ based on resolution and sequence identity. PDB codes of selected proteins are listed below.

3P09_A, 3PG4_A, 3GSG_A, 1W7F_A, 1I2S_A, 3S1Y_A, 1FR6_A, 3LY3_A, 1JTG_A, 1JTD_A, 4BLM_A, 3BFD_A, 1SHV_A, 2QZ6_A, 3L6N_A, 2ZC7_A, 3P98_A, 3PY6_A, 1ZG4_A, 2G2W_A,

3C7V_A, 3RKK_A, 3BYD_A, 1GHI_A, 3QHY_A, 2CC1_A, 3SH8_A, 3DTM_A, 3LVZ_A, 1K4F_A, 4ZNB_A, 2XR0_A, 1GCE_A, 2GMN_A, 3CJM_A, 1K38_A, 3M2K_A, 2FU6_A, 2ZO4_A, 3ZR9_A, 3QI0_A, 1BC2_A, 3GMW_A, 1ZC2_A, 1PIO_A, 1IYS_A, 2YZ3_A, 1WUP_A, 1FOF_B, 3OZH_A, 1N4O_A, 2P4Z, 1Q2Q_A, 1RGY_A, 1H8Z_A, 1MBL_A, 2A3U_A, 1ZKJ_A, 1Y54_A, 1DD6_A, 1M2X_A, 1JJE_A, 2A49_A, 3G4P_A, 2WRS_A, 1E25_A, 2V20_A, 1DDK_A, 2ZJ9_A, 1L9Y_A, 1HTZ_A, 1HZO_A, 3GMV_X, 1O7E_A, 1M6K_A, 3S0Z_A, 1S0W_A, 3H3E_A, 2WGI_A, 2DKF_A, 3IF6_A, 1ZKP_B, 3C5A_A, 3PAE_A, 2FHX_A, 3DW0_A, 3R2U_A.

Cation- π interactions :

We exploit the server cation- π trends using realistic electrostatics program (CAPTURE)¹ for calculating energetics of cation- π interactions.

Computation of hydrophobicity and conformational preferences of residues involved in cation- π interactions :

Hydrophobicity of cation- π interacting residues was analyzed using the program NETASA⁷. Conformational preference of interacting residues was analyzed by utiliz-

ing the data obtained from PDB.

Analysis of preferential contact between interacting residues :

Preferential contacts between the interacting residues are examined to analyze the contribution of cation- π interacting residues in the global and local conformational stability of β -lactamases.

Locating the stabilizing regions cation- π interacting residues :

SCide server was used to locate the stabilizing regions in β -lactamases⁸.

Functional importance of interacting residues :

Functional importance of cation- π interacting residues was calculated using ConSurf server⁹ and the residues are categorized based on the score from 1 to 9.

Contribution of cation- π interaction in the binding site of β -lactamases :

Contribution of cation- π interaction in the binding site of β -lactamases was analyzed using the program LIGPLOT¹⁰.

Results and discussion

Energetics of cation- π interactions :

Our result showed that a sum of 240 favorable cation- π interactions. The outcome of our study signifies that, the contribution of Arg is higher in cationic residues whereas Tyr dominates in π residues. The compositions of six interacting pairs are represented in Fig. 1. The highest contribution of energy is observed with Arg 258

Fig. 1. Pairwise interactions of cation- π interacting residues in β -lactamases.

Fig. 2. Highest energetic contribution between the residues Arg 258 and Trp 289 of PDB ID 3P98.

and Trp 289 residues of PDB ID 3P98. Pictorial representation of the interaction is shown in Fig. 2.

Computation of hydrophobicity and conformational preferences of residues involved in cation- π interaction :

Solvent accessibility pattern of cation- π interacting residues shows that substantial number of amino acids involved in interactions is located on the surface of proteins, thereby contributing stability to the terminus region of β -lactamases. Conformational preference of cation- π residues shows that Arg and Phe prefer to be in strand, whereas Lys, Tyr and Trp prefer to be in helix conformation.

Locating the stabilizing regions in cation- π interacting residues :

Structural importance of cation- π interacting residues shows that around 30% of the interacting residues encompass more than one stabilizing regions. Hence these residues contribute significantly in maintaining the conformational constancy of β -lactamases.

Functional importance of cation- π interacting residues :

Functional importance of cation- π interacting residues is analyzed and our results depicts that nearly 40% of the interacting residues are highly conserved as indicated by the grade scale of ConSurf server. This finding reveals the importance of cation- π interacting residues in the specificity of β -lactamases.

Contribution of cation- π interaction in the binding site of β -lactamases :

Since the numbers of cation- π interactions are minimal in the binding site of β -lactamases, these residues

contribute more to the stability of β -lactamases than substrate binding.

Conclusion

Our study provides valuable information on the stability pattern of β -lactamases, which will be useful for the development of safe and effective drugs.

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